

85 - THE LEVEL OF PARTICIPATION OF THE STATE IN THE ADMINISTRATION OF THE BRAZILIAN SPORT AS A FACTOR FOR SOCIAL INCLUSION OF DEFICIENCY BEARERS

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Scenery

Historically, the deficiency bearers live an exclusion in the society, with reflexes for their physical and mental health. After a long obscurantism period, a better attention is observed to those individuals all over the world.

Several reasons can be attributed to this new phase of interest. Immediately two can be mentioned: 1. Those individuals' discovery for the marketing agents, since according to CHRISTOPHER (1999), the relationship force with the customers is the most valuable of any managerial organization; and 2. The increase of the pressure level for the rulers to leave of the speech and place into practice social inclusion politics, as pointed out by PETTENGILL (2001), affirming that "the constitutional and infra-constitutional legal devices determine to the public power and their organs, to assure to the deficiency bearers the full exercise of their basic rights and of others that propitiate their personal, social and economical well-being."

TUBINO (1996) verified that in Brazil, the practice of sports for deficiency bearers was only increased in late 1980 decade, what demonstrates the Brazilian immaturity to work with such important subject.

Objective

To analyze the relevance of the federal sporting administration, for the sport to be effectively institutionalized for individuals bearing deficiency, as instrument of social inclusion.

Methodology

Regarding its ends, it was a descriptive research for exposing characteristics of a certain population or phenomenon and regarding its means, it was an applied research, once it is fundamentally motivated by the need of solving concrete problems, more immediate or not (VERGARA, 1998).

Limitation

As a descriptive research, it does not have any commitment in explaining the phenomena that it relates, although it serves as base for such explanation.

Deficiency and its bearers

The term incapacity synthesizes a great number of different functional limitations permanent or transitory enrolled in populations worldwide. This incapacity can come under the form of a physical, intellectual or sensorial deficiency; of a disease that requires medical care or of a mental illness (PETTENGILL, 2001a).

Deficiency bearer is the one who presents, in permanent character, abnormalities or losses of his/hers structure or function psychological, physiologic or anatomical, that generate incapacity to develop activities, inside a pattern considered as normal for human beings (Art. 3º, Decreto Federal nº 914, de 6 de setembro de 1993).

Exclusion and social inclusion

ROSADAS (1989), affirms that today it is still discussed all over the world, stimulated by scientific knowledge, what should be done for such different individuals that sometimes move inordinately, don't fasten their attention, can present many combined sequels, and so, framing a complex and compromising picture.

THE EXCLUSION PROCESS

Exclusion is just a moment of the perception that each one and all of us can have of things that concretely are translated in privation: employment privation, privation of means to participate in the consumption market, well-being privation, privation of rights, privation of freedom, privation of hope (MARTINS, 1997). For DUPAS (1999), social exclusion is a multidimensional phenomenon that extrapolates the poverty dimensions, while viewed as an income, being diagnosed through other dimensions such as health, education, leisure, environmental quality, politics, economy, etc.

THE INCLUSION AS SOCIAL RANSOM

According to SPOSATI (1996), the inclusion characterizes the reach of a minimum pattern that would guarantee access to the universe of the four basic utopias: autonomy of income, human development, life quality and justness.

"Autonomy of Income is the citizen's capacity to supply his vital, cultural, politics and social needs, under the respect conditions to the individual and collective ideas linked to the market and importing the individual's and State's responsibilities.

Life's Quality involves the democratization of the accesses to the conditions of the man's preservation, of the nature and of the environment, implicating in a better redistribution of the social and technological richness to the citizens and reduction of the degradation and environmental precariousness.

Human development is the citizens' possibility to develop their intellectual potential with a small privation degree, i.e., the collectively use of the highest degree of human capacity.

Justness is the execution of the equality and access to the rights of the population, the possibility of the manifestation of the differences in being respected without discrimination."

For MARTINS (1997), the current economical politics, in Brazil and in countries, that proceed what it is being called neo-liberal model, implicate the deliberate precarious and unstable inclusion, marginal. They are not, properly, exclusion politics. They are politics of the people's inclusion in the economical processes, in the production and in the circulation of goods and services, in strict terms of what is rationally convenient and necessary to the most efficient (and cheap) reproduction of the capital.

Sport and social inclusion

Nowadays, the sport relies on the foundations of the physical activity, to take health and life quality to those practicing who are directed to the correct form of its use (MATSUDO, 1999).

It is understood as Inclusive Sporting Activity, every activity that considers the potentialities and limitations physical-motors, sensorial and mental of those who practice it, propitiates the effective participation in several recreational sporting activities and, consequently, the development of all their potentialities (COSTA e BITTAR, 2002). In an inclusive perspective, it

is not enough to just know the characteristics in the physical aspects, but it is necessary the understanding of their relationships with other participants, with the physical activities and/or sportive and the meaning of those activities for the deficiency bearer.

Legislation, deficiency bearer and sport

As of the decade of 1970 it began to appear countless manifestations all over the world that culminate in laws that started to assure, in a punctual way, rights to the deficiency bearers population. The Brazilian Federal Constitution (1988) assures several rights and mechanisms that seek to offer the conditions of social justice for the deficient people, such as: health care; discrimination prohibition; individual warranties, protection; social integration; social attendance; qualification and rehabilitation; education; specialized attendance; accessibility and adaptation of facilities.

Legislations and important sporting manifestations in international level

The "International Letter of the Physical Education and Sports", of 1978, the General Assembly of 10th Physical Education Pan-American Congress, of (1986) (LÓPEZ e SAFONS, 1996), and Fédération Internationale d'Education Physique (FIEP), in the "World Manifests of the Physical Education" of 2000 (13), detach the physical education practice and the sport as fundamental right and that it should be offered special opportunities of practice to the people with some kind of deficiency in the fight against the discrimination and any kind of social exclusion.

Main legislations and resolutions in national level

The Federal Ordinance nr 914/1993, recommends the person's deficiency bearer inclusion and includes the sport among the initiatives. The Law nr 9.615, dated March 24, 1998 Know as "Lei Pelé" (4) foresees among other things, the elaboration of a project of fomentation of sport practice for deficiency bearers. The Ordinance nr 3.298, dated December 20, 1999 (6), precisely approaches the theme "sport and leisure" and seeks to make it possible the practice of physical activity without restrictions. There is, also, regulations and state and municipal laws on the subject.

Discussing the government administration of the Brazilian sport

For FERREIRA and BOTOMÉ (1984), contradictorily to a lack of attendance, characteristic to the deficient people of the third world, in Brazil, many services are available and, at the same time, the population lacks them. This because to be available doesn't mean to be accessible. It is responsibility of the society and, especially, of the Federal Government, to join efforts to the sport dissemination, aiming to gather access to every citizen, indistinctly.

It is important to the Federal Government in trying to reach the exact definition of its goals, deciding the best means to reach them, evaluate the obtained results and use an efficient mechanism to check the effects, everything as indicator of evaluation to the administration process that is predominantly associated to the social "profits".

To AZEVEDO (1999), "the ideological and symbolic codes have been implicit also in the duty of legitimation and accumulating of the Estate, even if the points of contact with soccer may not be so clear. If these duties have such explaining way socially speaking, on what concerns to soccer, for example, the actuation of the Estate was

THE LOCATION OF THE SPORT IN THE GOVERNMENT'S MINISTRIES

The study performed by the technician of the Sports Ministry Rivaldo Araújo da Silva, in 2003, leads to the to the verification that the sport in Brazil in spite of your relevance it has not been provided in an appropriate and consistent way the whole population. The physical education, the sport, the recreation and the leisure, along the years, belonged to Ministry of Education and Culture (as of 1937); Secretariat of Sports of the Presidency of the Republic (as of 1990); Ministry of Education (as of 1992); Ministry of the Extraordinary State of the Sports (as of 1995); Ministry of Education and of the Sport (as of 1998); Ministry of the Sport and Tourism (as of 1999); Ministry of the Sport (as of 2003).

From January 1990 to December 2002, 12 (twelve) sports secretaries were nominated, in the same period that government had three presidents, being two in a same mandate (Fernando Collor de Melo and Itamar Franco) and one for two consecutive mandates (Fernando Henrique Cardoso). This give us an average of four secretaries per mandate. Important fact is that, in that same period, the sport was linked to seven different places of federal ministries.

The professional administration of the sport in the process of social inclusion

One of the important points to be observed to professionalize the administration of the sport by the Federal Government, is the application of the concept of relational competence, which is incrementing value to something that, until little time ago, did not have relevance and that is an activity that guarantees the organization survival (CHRISTOPHER, 1999). Thus, it is necessary to accomplish a conception change and pass to respect the human being, the moral and ethical attitudes, the products and services; elements that previously did not have importance.

According to AZEVEDO, generally speaking, from 1995 to 2002, the federal public management of Brazilian sports showed a scarce administrative planning and a reality of too little motivation concerning future.

Conclusions

Nor less or more important than other actions, the sport comes as one of the indispensable requirements for individuals to reach the total dimension of the social inclusion. This can be proven once the sport is a simple instrument, accessible, cheap and efficient, be it in recreational level, or regarding to high performance competition, what contributes a lot to the individual's social inclusion.

The enormous alternation of links of the sport with several ministries of the federal government which is sharply observed in the period between 1995-2002 and by itself it is an invitation to the reflection about the existence of an administration that leads to important social results for a population that lacks from effective actions of the government.

From the model of administration of the programs and available resources in offering physical activity in all levels for those who bear special needs is that it will depend the results desired for the strengthen of this stage of the social inclusion's process. The sport, since it is aligned with a complex social politics that includes government and society, can become a powerful contributory tool for the social inclusion's process of deficiency bearers.

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THE LEVEL OF PARTICIPATION OF THE STATE IN THE ADMINISTRATION OF THE BRAZILIAN SPORT AS A FACTOR FOR SOCIAL INCLUSION OF DEFICIENCY BEARERS

Abstract

This study aimed to analyze the relevance of the sporting administration in federal level, in effectively institutionalize the sports to individuals bearing deficiencies, as an important instrument of social inclusion. Methodologically, regarding its ends, it was a descriptive research and referring to the means, it was an applied research. Historically the sport is not represented and does not have relevance within the federal structures, what can be proven for the great linkage of alternation with several sectors of the administration. Along the times and in all human history, the access to the sport by individuals bearing deficiencies was always limited by structural barriers, equipments and, essentially, of social order. The research verified that the fact that the sport does not have a specific identification in the government structure, commits any sporting public politics, with reflexes even more expressive in the initiatives addressed to the individuals bearing deficiencies, whose representativeness and political influence for the own situation of the deficiency are much more inferior to the other organized sporting groups. The existence of a specific ministry to drift and manage the national sport points out, in thesis, to a larger attention for groups with less potential of political influence, but of extreme social prominence.

Key Words: 1. Sporting administration; 2. Health; 3. Bearer of Deficiency.

LE NIVEAU DE PARTICIPATION DE L'ÉTAT DANS LA GESTION DU SPORT BRÉSILIEU COMME FACTEUR D'INCLUSION SOCIALE DE PERSONNES PORTEURS DE HANDICAP

Résumé

Cette étude a eu pour objectif d'analyser l'importance de la gestion sportive au niveau fédéral, pour que le sport soit effectivement institutionnalisé aux individus porteurs de handicap, comme important instrument d'inclusion sociale. Méthodologiquement, pour ce qui est des buts, cela a été une recherche descriptive et pour ce qui est des moyens cela a été une recherche appliquée. Historiquement, le sport n'a pas de représentativité et de grande valeur dans les structures fédérales, ce qui peut être prouvé par la grande alternance de lien avec les plus divers secteurs de l'administration. Au long des époques et dans toute l'humanité, l'accès au sport par les individus porteurs de handicap a toujours été limité par des barrières de structure, d'équipements et, essentiellement, d'ordre social. La recherche a constaté que le fait que le sport ne possède pas d'identification spécifique dans la structure gouvernementale compromet n'importe quelle politique publique sportive, avec des reflets encore plus expressifs dans les initiatives relatives aux individus porteurs de déficience, dont les représentativités et influence politique par la propre situation de déficience sont très inférieures à celles d'autres groupes sportifs organisés. L'existence d'un ministère spécifique pour planifier et gérer le sport national montre, en théorie, une plus grande attention aux groupes avec un plus petit potentiel d'influence politique, mais d'extrême éminence sociale.

Mots-clés : 1. Administration Sportive ; 2. Santé ; 3. Porteur de handicap.

EL NIVEL DE PARTICIPACIÓN DEL ESTADO EN LA ADMINISTRACIÓN DEL DEPORTE BRASILEÑO COMO EL FACTOR DE INCLUSIÓN SOCIAL DE LAS PERSONAS PORTADORAS DE DEFICIENCIA

Resumen

Este estudio apuntó a analizar la relevancia de la administración deportiva en el nivel federal, para que el deporte sea efectivamente institucionalizado a los individuos portadores de deficiencia, como el instrumento importante de inclusión social. Metodológicamente, cuanto a los fines fue una pesquisa descriptiva, y con la relación a los medios una pesquisa aplicada. Históricamente el deporte no tiene representatividad y relevancia dentro de las estructuras federales. A lo largo de las épocas y en toda la humanidad, el acceso al deporte para los individuos portadores de deficiencia siempre fue limitado por las barreras estructurales, de materiales y, esencialmente, de orden social. La pesquisa verificó que el hecho del deporte no tener una identificación específica en la estructura gubernamental compromete cualquier política pública deportiva, con los reflejos todavía más expresivos en las iniciativas dirigidas a los portadores de deficiencia, cuya representatividad y influencia política, por la propia situación de la deficiencia, son mucho más inferiores a las de otros grupos deportivos organizados. La existencia de un ministerio específico para planear y administrar el deporte nacional apunta, en tesis, a una atención más grande a los grupos con menor potencial de influencia política, pero de extrema prominencia social.

Palabras llave: 1. Administración deportiva; 2. Salud; 3. Portador de Deficiencia.

O NÍVEL DE PARTICIPAÇÃO DO ESTADO NA GESTÃO DO ESPORTE BRASILEIRO COMO FATOR DE INCLUSÃO SOCIAL DE PESSOAS PORTADORAS DE DEFICIÊNCIA

Resumo

Este estudo objetivou analisar a relevância da gestão esportiva em nível federal, para que o esporte seja efetivamente institucionalizado a indivíduos portadores de deficiência, como importante instrumento de inclusão social. Metodologicamente, quanto aos fins foi uma pesquisa descritiva e quanto aos meios foi uma pesquisa aplicada. Historicamente o esporte não tem representatividade e relevância dentro das estruturas federais, o que pode ser comprovado pela grande alternância de vinculação com os mais diversos setores da administração. Ao longo das épocas e em toda a humanidade, o acesso ao esporte pelos indivíduos portadores de deficiência sempre foi limitado por barreiras estruturais, de equipamentos e, essencialmente, de ordem social. A pesquisa constatou que o fato de o esporte não possuir uma identificação específica na estrutura governamental compromete qualquer política pública esportiva, com reflexos ainda mais expressivos nas iniciativas direcionadas aos indivíduos portadores de deficiência, cujas representatividades e influência política pela própria situação da deficiência são muito inferiores às de outros grupos esportivos organizados. A existência de um ministério específico para planejar e gerir o esporte nacional aponta, em tese, para uma atenção maior para os grupos com menor potencial de influência política, mas de extrema eminência social.

Palavras-chave: 1. Administração Esportiva; 2. Saúde; 3. Portador de Deficiência.